

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones. Part—VI†

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5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone(Ia) and 7-allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone(Id) on acetylation followed by bromination and cyclization with alcoholic potassium hydroxide afforded 5'-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(3',2'-5,6)-xanthone(II) and 5,5'-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(2',3'-6,7)xanthone(III) respectively. 8-Allyl-7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one(IVc) under similar condition gave 6-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxybenzofuran-5'-yl)-6-oxo-6H-hexanoic acid(VI) instead of the expected 8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) furo(2,3-h)-benzopyran-4-one(V). Attempted synthesis of (V) through cyclization of (IVc) with conc. sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal or DDQ failed since dehydrogenation could not be achieved.

THE present work was undertaken with a view to synthesise furobenzopyrones with a fused five or six membered ring system through the addition of bromine to *o*-acetoxyallyl derivatives, subsequent cyclization and dehydrobromination with alcoholic alkali following the method of Adams and Rindfus¹. It was observed that in the course of cyclization and dehydrobromination with alcoholic alkali to form furobenzopyrone, the fused six membered ring system remained intact, while in the case of fused five membered ring system, it underwent desired cyclization to furan ring with simultaneous opening of γ -pyrone ring and five membered ring to form 6-oxo-6H-hexanoic acid derivative.

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone(Ia)² and 7-allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone(Id)² on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine gave corresponding 6-acetoxy derivatives (Ib) and (Ic) respectively. On bromination with bromine in glacial acetic acid they yielded 5-(2'-3'-dibromopropyl)-(Ic) and 7-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-(If) derivative respectively. (Ic) and (If) on treatment with alcoholic potassium hydroxide in boiling water bath afforded 5'-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(3',2'-5,6)xanthone(II), and 5,5'-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(2',3'-6,7)xanthone(III) respectively.

On thermal condensation with ethylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate in boiling diphenyl ether³ resorcinol gave 7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(IVa). This on allylation followed by Claisen migration gave 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(IVc), which on treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine furnished 7-acetoxyderivative(IVd). On treatment with bromine in acetic acid (IVd) yielded corresponding 8-(2',3'-dibromopropyl) derivative(IVe). The cyclization and dehydrobromination of (IVe) was achieved by alcoholic potassium hydroxide on boiling water bath but the product

obtained was not 8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-4-one(V) but 6-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxybenzofuran-5'-yl)-6-oxo-6H-hexanoic acid (VI), the structure of which was confirmed by NMR(CF₃COOH) signals at δ 1.9 δ (4H, br.t, C₃-H₂ and C₄-H₂), 2.47 (3H, s, C₂'-CH₃), 2.59-2.72 (2H, m, C₂-H₂), 3.0-3.3 (2H, m, C₅-H₂), 6.70 (1H, s, C₈'-H), 7.1 (1H, d, J=10Hz, C₇'-H) and 7.78 (1H, d, J=10Hz, C₆'-H).

8-Allyl-7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one(IVc) was treated with conc. sulphuric acid to give 8-methyl-1,2,3,4,8,9-hexahydrocyclopenta(b) furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-4-one(VII). This could not be dehydrogenated to 8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) furo(2,3-h) benzopyran-4-one(V) by using palladised charcoal (10%) or DDQ.

- (Ia) R = -CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁ = R₂ = H
 (Ib) R = -CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁ = -COCH₃, R₂ = H
 (Ic) R = -CH₂CHBrCH₂Br, R₁ = -COCH₃, R₂ = H
 (Id) R = CH₃, R₁ = H, R₂ = -CH₂CH=CH₂
 (Ie) R = CH₃, R₁ = -COCH₃, R₂ = -CH₂CH=CH₂
 (If) R = CH₃, R₁ = -COCH₃, R₂ = -CH₂CHBrCH₂Br

(II)

(III)

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- (IVa) R = R₁ = H
 (IVb) R = H, R₁ = -CH₂OH = CH₂
 (IVc) R = -CH₂OH = CH₂, R₁ = H
 (IVd) R = -CH₂OH = CH₂, R₁ = -COCH₃
 (IVe) R = -CH₂OHBrCH₂Br, R₁ = -COCH₃

Experimental

PMR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. Uv spectra were determined on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer.

5-Allyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (Ib): A mixture of 5-allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (1.5 g) and acetic anhydride (6 ml) containing a few drops of pyridine was heated on a water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice containing hydrochloric acid (2 ml). The separated product (Ib) was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 126°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 72.19; H, 5.87; C₁₈H₁₈O₄, requires C, 72.49; H, 6.04%).

5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (Ic): A solution of bromine (0.32 g) in glacial acetic acid (6 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of (Ib) (0.6 g) in glacial acetic acid (8 ml) over a period of 1 hr at room temperature. After being stirred for further 1 hr the solution was diluted with ice cold water and allowed to stand. The product (Ic) which separated was filtered, dissolved in ethanol and decolourised by activated charcoal. It crystallised as colourless needles from ethanol, m.p. 171-72°, (sintering from 166° and decomposed to a dark black melt at 175°), yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 47.23; H, 4.34; Br, 35.41; C₁₈H₁₈Br₂O₄ requires C, 47.17; H, 3.93; Br, 34.93%).

5'-Methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(3',2'-5,6)xanthone (II): A solution of 5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (0.46 g) in ethanolic potassium hydroxide (0.3 g) in 20 ml absolute alcohol was refluxed for 2 hr. Water (60 ml) was added and the solution immediately acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The separated product was extracted with ethyl acetate and washed with aqueous ammonia (10%) and water. It crystallised from benzene as shining colourless needles, m.p. 169-70°; yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 75.86; H, 5.40; C₁₆H₁₄O₄ requires C, 75.60; H, 5.56%); nmr (CDCl₃): δ 1.58-2.05 (4H, m, C₂-H₂ and C₈-H₂), 2.50 (3H, s, C₅'-CH₃), 2.40-2.87 (4H, m, C₁-H₂ and C₄-H₂), 6.65 (1H, s, C₄'-H), 7.35 (1H, d, J = 10Hz, C₇-H) and 8.02 (1H, d, J = 10Hz, C₈-H).

7-Allyl-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (Ie): 7-Allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone² (2 g), acetic anhydride (8 ml) and a few drops of pyridine were heated on a water bath for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 128°, yield 1.7 g. (Found: C, 72.46; H, 6.40; C₁₉H₂₀O₄ requires C, 73.07; H, 6.41%).

7-(2',3'-Dibromopropyl)-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (If): A solution of 7-allyl-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (1.25 g) in glacial acetic acid (8 ml) was treated with bromine (0.64 g) in glacial acetic acid (13 ml). The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 146° (decom.), yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 48.29; H, 4.08; Br, 33.53; C₁₉H₂₀O₄Br₂ requires C, 48.31; H, 4.24; Br, 33.90%).

5,5'-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(2',3'-6,7)xanthone (III): 7-(2',3'-Dibromopropyl)-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthon-6-yl acetate (0.5 g) was refluxed for 5 hr with a solution of potassium hydroxide (0.3 g) in absolute alcohol (20 ml). The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The solid thus obtained was subjected to column chromatography. Elution with chloroform yielded (III), crystallising from acetic acid, m.p. 223°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 76.07; H, 5.52; C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 76.12; H, 5.97%); ir: 830 cm⁻¹ (furan), 1630 cm⁻¹ (γ-pyronyl) C=O group; UV λ_{max}^{Chloroform}: 252 (log e 4.94), 290 (4.26) and 326 nm (4.38).

7-Hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one (IVa): A mixture of resorcinol (3 g) and ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (4.5 ml) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (6 ml) for 3 hr with a short condenser to facilitate the removal of alcohol formed. After cooling, the separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 288°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 71.52; H, 5.35; C₁₉H₁₆O₄ requires C, 71.29; H, 4.95%); ir: 1645 (>C=O) and 3225 cm⁻¹ (-OH). The product (IVa) (0.5 g) on treatment with acetic anhydride (4 ml) and pyridine (0.2 ml) gave an acetyl derivative, which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles, m.p. 136°, yield 0.45 g. (Found C,

69.43 ; H, 5.40 ; $C_{14}H_{13}O_4$ requires C, 68.85 ; H, 4.92% ; nmr ($CDCl_3$) : δ 1.94-2.24 (2H, m, C_2-H_2) 2.30 (3H, s, $OCOCH_3$), 2.67-3.05 (4H, m, C_1-H_2 and C_8-H_2), 7.04-7.24 (2H, m, C_6-H and C_8-H), 8.21 (1H, d, $J=10Hz$, C_5-H).

7-Allyloxy-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one (IVb) : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one (2 g), allyl bromide (1.2 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (6 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml) on a water bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into water. The separated product was extracted with ether and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide to remove unreacted compound. It crystallised from benzene-light petroleum, m.p. 112°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 74.33 ; H, 5.76 ; $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.39 ; H, 5.78%).

8-Allyl-7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one (IVc) : 7-Allyloxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one (2 g) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (6 ml) for 8 hr. The separated crystalline product was filtered and washed with a mixture of light petroleum and benzene. The product thus obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 267°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 73.92 ; H, 5.84 ; $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.39 ; H, 5.79%). ir : 1640 ($>C=O$) and 3085 cm^{-1} (broad, $-OH$).

8-Allyl-4-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-7-yl acetate (IVd) : This was prepared by heating 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one (1.2 g) with acetic anhydride (8 ml) and a few drops of pyridine and obtained as needles from alcohol, m.p. 158°, yield 1 g. (Found : C, 71.80 ; H, 5.73 ; $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.83 ; H, 5.63%).

8-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-4-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)-benzopyran-7-yl acetate (IVe) : A solution of bromine (0.32 g) in glacial acetic acid (7 ml) was allowed to react with a solution of 8-allyl-4-oxo-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-7-yl acetate (0.57 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml). The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The solid which separated was crystallised as small needles from alcohol, m.p. 162° (decomp.) (Found : C, 46.22 ; H, 3.73 ; Br, 35.85 ; $C_{17}H_{16}O_4Br_2$ requires C, 45.94 ; H, 3.60 ; Br, 36.03%).

Attempted synthesis of 8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) furo(2,3-h) benzopyran-4-one(V) : 8-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-4-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-7-yl acetate (0.45 g) when refluxed in absolute alcohol (25 ml) in presence of potassium hydroxide (0.25 g) for 4 hr gave 6-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxybenzofuran-5'-yl)-6-oxo-6H-hexanoic acid(VI), which crystallised from ethanol as white prism, m.p. 149°-50°, yield 0.2 g. It was soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated on addition of acid and gave red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 64.90 ; H, 5.64 ; $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.21 ; H, 5.79%) ; ir : 835 (furan ring), 1645 ($>C=O$), 1730 ($-COOH$) and a broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} ($-OH$).

8-Methyl-1,2,3,4,8,9-hexahydrocyclopenta(b) furo(2,3-h)-benzopyran-4-one(VII) : 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b) benzopyran-4-one (1 g) was triturated with sulphuric acid (90% ; 5 ml) on a water bath for 15 minutes. The content was poured into crushed ice, the separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 178°. yield 0.8 g (Found : C, 74.36 ; H, 5.45 ; $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.39 ; H, 5.78%). ir : 1635 (γ -propyl $>C=O$ group) ; UV $\lambda_{max}^{Methanol}$: 248 (log e 4.29), 256 (4.32), 300 nm (4.12), nmr($CDCl_3$) : δ 1.52(3H, d, $J=7Hz$, C_8-CH_3), 1.95-2.29 and 2.70-3.08 (two br. m, 6H, cyclopentanone ring protons), 2.80-3.62 (m, 2H, C_9-H_2), 4.94-5.2 (m, 1H, C_8-H), 6.80 (1H, d, $J=10Hz$, C_6-H), 8.06 (1H, d, $J=10Hz$, C_5-H).

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